

TECHNICAL AND PHYSICAL PREPARATION OF STUDENT GIRLS DEVELOPMENT THROUGH NATIONAL AND ACTION GAMES

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Abstract. This article reflects the fact that the use of national and movement games to improve the technical and physical fitness of female students has led to a positive change in their level of technical and physical fitness in sports.

Key words: games, national, competition, intensity, load, competition, performance, endurance, technique, optimum, globalization, jump.

РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ И ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВОЧЕК-СТУДЕНТОК С ПОМОЩЬЮ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ИГР И ЭКШН-ИГР

Аннотация. В этой статье отражен тот факт, что использование национальных игр и подвижных игр для улучшения технической и физической подготовленности студенток привело к положительному изменению их уровня технической и физической подготовленности в спорте.

Ключевые слова: игры, национальные, соревнование, интенсивность, нагрузка, соревнование, производительность, выносливость, техника, оптимум, глобализация, прыжок.

Introduction.

To create a healthy lifestyle in our country, to create conditions for the population, especially women and girls, to regularly engage in physical education and sports, to instill confidence in women and girls in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions. Strengthening, courage and patriotism, developing feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, as well as systematic organization of selection of talented athletes from among women and girls, as well as large-scale work aimed at further development of physical education and sports are being carried out. Countries of the world paying great attention to the field of physical education and sports, at the level of state policy, systematic work is being carried out on the issues of forming a healthy lifestyle and health protection among the population, increasing the prestige of the country in sports and increasing the fame of the country in international sports events.

Currently, as a result of the rapid development of science, in the training of qualified athletes, sports experts and scientists are required to apply new advanced technologies to the training process and to constantly monitor it. In order to further develop physical education and sports in the territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to attract all layers of the population, especially women, to regularly engage in physical education and sports, and to increase the effectiveness of the effective use of the conditions created in this regard in our country, a number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted. I was done.

For example, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated January 24, 2020 No. PF5924 "On measures to improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", March 14, 2022 "Gymnastics "On measures

to establish the Oksana Chusovitina school of sports skills" No. great attention is paid to the issues of conducting activities.

National and action games have a great role in strengthening the health of female students through physical education and sports, increasing the level of physical fitness and improving their ability to work. Various national and active games are important for the development of young people, becoming mature and healthy in all aspects and developing their physical qualities.

It determines a certain level of movement speed in the development of technical and physical fitness of female students, and this process is also of great importance in competitions and competitions that require speed and agility. To improve the speed and agility of students, we tried to improve the technical and physical fitness of female students using national and action games inherited from our ancestors.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Human civilization, which is the absolute chain of the historical development of the distant past, has such pillars and cornerstones that preserve the harmony, development and continuity of the past, present and future, and are passed down from generation to generation as a legacy. reaches the level of taste and values. Such arguments are proved by historical works such as "Avesta", "Alpomish", "Gorogli", "Tomaris", "Qirq Kyz" and the heroes of folklore. Continuing these values, we tried to increase the technical and physical fitness of our female students, using national and action games in the training process.

The problems of the use of national and movement games by the scientists of our country in the course of physical education classes of students of educational institutions in the scientific research of T.S. Usmonkhodzhayev, A.A.Pulatov, Sh.A.Pulatov, D.Kh. reflected.

As a result of studying the scientific and methodological literature of famous scientists, it became clear that a number of researches were conducted to improve the technical and physical fitness of female students. In particular, it is reflected in the scientific and methodological works of F.A. Kerimov, R.S. Salomov, Yu.M. Yunusova.

It is to improve the technical and physical fitness of female students.

Based on the goals and tasks of our research, we used the following national and action games to improve the technical and tactical preparation and physical qualities of female students in physical education classes and sports training:

- Pushing out of the circle;
- Team of agile feet;
- Running with filler balls;
- Three options ball;
- Ball passing by volleyball players;
- Planting potatoes;
- Geese are swans.

Through these national and action games, students improve their agility, quickness, quick strength, as well as develop their focus and accuracy.

The development of the main or special muscle groups formed in students as a result of national and mobile games depends on their comprehensive preparation. In physical education classes, students include the muscles that perform the main work in performing movements, as a result, special importance is also attached to the development of physical fitness.

As a result of the search for more effective means of developing individual muscle groups of female students, special exercises were used. Thus, our opinion that it is possible to train athletes with optimal sports form in all aspects by developing physical fitness of students was confirmed. The stamina and agility of female students is measured by the time they have continued to compete at a high level and the condition they have maintained throughout the competition.

CONCLUSION

Our research and literature analysis showed that physical fitness of female students is the main factor. It will be possible to develop and evaluate physical fitness indicators with the help of special tests. It is possible to note the existence of differences in terms of physical fitness indicators when female students compete in competitions. Based on the obtained results, it was determined that the development of physical fitness of students determines the speed of movement to a certain extent, and this process is also of great importance in competitions and competitions that require speed and agility. Based on our experience, it is possible to educate female athletes who have an optimal sports form in all aspects by developing technical and physical training of female students, if active games are used during regular training and in their free time. our opinion is confirmed. It is also possible to prevent injuries and injuries if the national and action games are used correctly during training.

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